

Intervention of China and China as A Factor on India-Bangladesh Relationship: A Study with Recent Trend

Paper Id : 17988 Submission Date : 15/08/2023 Acceptance Date : 22/08/2023 Publication Date : 25/08/2023

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8335665

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Pijush Kr. Khan
Research Scholar
Department Of Political
Science
Ram Krishna Dharmarth
Foundation
(RKDF)University
Ranchi,Jharkhand, India

Renuka Poodar
Assistant Professor
Department Of Political
Science
Ram Krishna Dharmarth
Foundation (RKDF)
University
Ranchi, Jharkhand, India

Abstract Bangladesh and India is close neighboring country sharing with common culture, heritage, language and long boundary. India is a first country who recognizes Bangladesh as an Independent sovereign country. But after assassination of Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, India Bangladesh relation was affected. Ziaur Rahman was taken Pro China attitude instead pro Indian attitude. After restoration of democracy in 1992, there were Begum Khaleda Zia became prime minister and taken China as a Close friend. But after that Sheikh Hasina assumed the power through 1996 Election and diplomacy of Bangladesh had been changed. In 2001, Bangladesh national party reelected, Begum Zia was prime minister. After that, China -Bangladesh signed various treaties, MOU especially in the defense sector. But recent time, India- China relation is not good. China is constantly trying to improve the relation with Bangladesh through the assistance of various projects in Bangladesh. There are also some irritations in India Bangladesh relation. China wants to get benefited from this irritation. India istaken various measures to prevent Chinese intervention in Bangladesh .India is trying to improve bilateral relationshipwith Bangladesh.

Keywords Diplomatic, Geostrategic, Conflict, Treaty, Connectivity, Displaced, Blood Neighbor.

Introduction India and Bangladesh remarked as a close blood neighbor there are numerous similarity between two countries from various aspect two countries have common history cultural heritage physiography Bangladesh has publicly acknowledge India's role in 1971 freedom movement and nation building of the country from 1972 India was one of the first country recognize government of Bangladesh but from 1972 there are ups and downs in India-Bangladesh relationships. there are various factor who is your affected into Bangladesh relation Dam on the various factor China is an important factor of India Bangladeshi relationships China also a neighboring state of India and Bangladesh people of Bangladesh and Society are very much affected from Bangladesh China relationships in 1971 Liberation war China was in Pakistan side and remarked as an "all-weather friends of Pakistan "and China gave veto against the UN membership to Bangladesh in the year 1972 .But from 1975 China Bangladesh relation history Kali increased in 1978 Chinese official paid their first visit in people Republic of Bangladesh in the year 2013 China launch belt and Road initiative and in 2016 Bangladesh officially join this belt and Road initiative and there are studying place in China Bangladesh relation now Bangladesh first trading partner is China instead India defense cooperation between two countries has been main area of cooperation do Bangladesh Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina assured India there will no impact on Indo Bangladesh relationship by China- Bangladesh relationships. Prime minister of Bangladesh also stated that Bangladesh India relationships as a "blood relationships".

Aim of study

1. To find out Historical Background of India- Bangladesh and Bangladesh- China Relationship.
2. To Examine Chia – Bangladesh partnership in various Sectors including defense, Economic and Development.
3. To analyses Chinese intervention in Indo- Bangladesh relationship.
4. To study India's response on Chinese intervention in Indo- Bangladesh friendly relation.
5. To find out some recommendation after concluding this study.

Review of Literature

Review of related literature help us to gain various knowledge of previous work in the same field. It also helps us to acquire knowledge different segment of respective fields. A researcher has Finds Research Gap of particular research by the help of Review of related literature. I, have reviews several literature in my study, some of them are briefing below-

Datta, sree Radha, Bangladesh Relation with china and India: A analysis, Institute of Defense studies and analysis,(September,2008) analyze influence of China in South Asia this comprehensive relation of Bangladesh China in contrast to India Bangladesh relation she has elaborately discuss rationalization of Bangladesh China relationships and its impact of on security of India and also impact of various bilateral agreement of India Bangladesh.

Ranjan ,Amit, "The Making of Bangladesh – China Relation" institute for south Asian studies , Singapore, discussed hegemony of South Asian small countries like Bangladesh is a Chinese strategies in present era. Historically they are not supported Liberation war of Bangladesh even they are opposed to freedom struggle of Bangladesh. When Bangladesh applied to United Nation for a membership, China provided veto power against Bangladesh. But trade between two countries has grown from 2002 when Bangladesh National Party formed government in Bangladesh. He also discuss about the China visit of H E Sheikh Hasina and several of agreement on infrastructure, power, development communication between China and Bangladesh. The author stated China's interest into Bangladesh as a matter of concern (Ranjan, Amit).

Kamruzzaman, Muhammad, International Journal of Social Science and human research, April 2021 in his article showed **Bangladesh China bilateral relation current trend analysis** an article when analyzed conceptual Framework with historical background of India China relation .The learned author try to find out various pattern of Bangladesh China relationship with a special reference to Sheikh Hasina period from 2009. He also discussed diplomatic aspect of bilateral relationship between Bangladesh and China and future area of cooperation.

Li,Amily ,Balancing India and China: the impact of foreign relation on Bangladesh (2018)Western University, discussed Bangladesh economic relation with India and China and which would be matter of tension for India, the second largest trading partner of Bangladesh. He analyzed summary of cooperation and conflict in India-Bangladesh relation and need of Bangladesh to grow Bangladesh -China relationships. Hefined Bangladeshi government initiative; try to balancing into economic power with India and China for its own interest.

DuttaDrSujit Kumar China Bangladesh India triangular cooperation option for Bangladesh journal of Indian Research (January to June 2021) try to analyzed new paradigm of cooperation among India, China Bangladesh .He stated Bangladesh as a geo strategic strongest country among the three countries i.e. India, Bangladesh, and China. Bangladesh having a strategic balance with India and China as two countries is equally important for Bangladesh

Islam Mohammad shariful and HussainDelwar 2021 understanding Bangladesh relation with India and China: dilemmas and response, journal of Indian Ocean region, briefly discussed China issue in India Bangladesh relation .The authors are find that, India and China have interest in Bangladesh for their presence as a leader of South Asian region .They also discussed in this paper India China clashed at the Galwan Valley in June 2020 and Sino- Indian contemporary border conflict. Competition of India and China over small country like Bangladesh in South Asia is being discussed.

The above mention literature analyzed china factors in India – Bangladesh relationship in various perspectives but according to me, there is no systematic analysis. **"Intervention of China and China as a factor on India -Bangladesh relationship: A Study with Recent Trend"**So, **Research Gap** has been found. There should necessary to analyze my topics in other perspective.

Methodology From the various method of study, I have chosen Historical, Analytical, Descriptive method of study. My research study is based on qualitative Research. Content analysis method has a major part in my study. I have used various government official report, press release and others reports. I have also taken various suggestions from the Expert of Foreign policy and Renewed Academician of Political Science and International relation. The whole Research work is done by Neoliberal theoretical Background.

Analysis

After doing Some Research Work in the topic, "Intervention of China and China as a factor on India -Bangladesh relationship: A Study with Recent Trend", I have fined various aspect of the study. Major Finding and analysis are given below-

India and Bangladesh share 4096 kilometer boundary (Bammi, YM, 2010). Two countries have same culture history and linguistic similar similarities. In 1947 undivided India divided into India and Pakistan. There was two parts of Pakistan East Pakistan and West Pakistan. There was huge difference in cultural linguistics and social structure between East and West Pakistan. There was unconditional dominance by West Pakistan on East Pakistan. So Liberation struggle was formed in East Pakistan. By the long history of Liberation struggle East Pakistan emerged as an independentNation Bangladesh in 1972 under the leadership of Bangabandhu Sheikh MujiburRahman. India Bangladesh relation was initiated by the first day of liberated Bangladesh. There was unconditional support of India behind the Liberation struggle of Bangladesh. Bangladesh publicly acknowledged many times role of India in their freedom movement. 1972 Indira Mujib treaty initiated a golden phase bilateral relation between India and Bangladesh. But in 1975 MujiburRahman was assassinated. After that Regime of general ZiaurRahman and Hussain Muhammad Ershad was not friendly for India. After 1992 democracy restoration in Bangladesh, but Bangladesh national party under the prime minister ship of Begum Khaleda Zia assumed the powers of Bangladesh. Mrs. was Pro Pakistani and Pro China minded. After that in 1996 Awami league was assume the power, Sheikh Hasina the daughter of bangabandhu Sheikh MujiburRahman became a prime minister of Bangladesh. But in 2001 election BNP leaded by Begum Khaleda Zia recapture the power of Bangladesh. From this time Begum Khaleda Zia was signed various deals with China. After (2006 to 2008), administration of caretaker government of Bangladesh comparative improved. In 2009, Bangladesh Awami League was reelected by the people of Bangladesh. From 2009 there is continuous improvement of Indo- Bangladesh relationship. But recent time there is presence of Chinese intervention in India Bangladesh relationship. Even Awami league government ,under the prime minister ship of Sheikh Hasina demanding various assistant from China which is a major concern for government of India.